

Group and the operation.

Group A
R[Ev]

Groups
0 ↓ 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, ...

G[E]	0 0	105	2010	3015	4020	5025
	10 3	40	70	100	130	160
	20 6	22	32	42	52	62
G[E]	16 5	46	76	106	136	166
	24 7	52	82	112	142	172
R[E]	3 6	16	26	36	46	56
	28 9	58	88	118	148	178
	4 8	18	28	38	48	58
X	1 34	64	94	124	154	

	Parity	L	R	
5	●	○		
10	○	●		
15	●	○		
20	○	○		
25	●	○		
30	○	●		
35	●	○		
40	○	○		N_k of $k(0,0)$
45	●	○		$N_{1,0}$ of $5(0,0)$
50	○	●		$N_{2,0}$ or $15(0,0)$
55	●	○		...
60	○	○	△	$N_k k(0,0)$
65	●	○		
70	○	●		

- Rules (Axiom) Parity affects
1. Left parity numbers will leave the group once transferred
 2. Right parity turns → transfer to left parity.
 3. Perfect parity will remain perfect till it reaches 20. then it turns to 10 which is right
 4. An numbers or △ Parity will stay △ till 30 which is right